

CONTEMPORARY TRENDS AND LEGAL FRAMEWORKS OF CONCILIATION PROCEDURES IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article analyzes the effectiveness of resolving disputes between business entities through mutual agreement, its advantages, the legal framework of the ongoing reforms in the judicial and legal system of our country, the concept of the settlement agreement and the mediation agreement procedures prescribed in Chapter 16 of the Economic Procedural Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan under the name of conciliation procedures, their legal and scientific definitions, as well as the role of these procedures in resolving disputes, the existing shortcomings in the regulation of these relations and the solutions proposed by the author to eliminate them.

Keywords: Alternative dispute resolution methods, conciliation procedures, settlement agreement, mediation agreement.

The current stage of reforms in the field aimed at improving the interaction of state bodies with the population, ensuring reliable protection of the rights and freedoms of citizens, and introducing modern mechanisms for resolving their problems, requires the creation of a unified system for pre-trial consideration of disputes in state bodies, as well as transforming mediation, arbitration courts and international arbitrations into effective alternative institutions that enjoy the trust of citizens and entrepreneurs to resolve disputes. This necessity is reflected in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Measures to Further Improve the Mechanisms for Alternative Dispute Resolution" No. PP-4754,

which outlines a number of tasks to carry out fundamental reforms in this area¹.

The 15th goal of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Strategy of Actions for the Development of the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" dated January 28, 2022 No. PF-60 is to create the necessary organizational and legal conditions for the widespread use of alternative dispute resolution methods and further expand the scope of application of the reconciliation institution.

Accordingly, one of the main tasks set in order to effectively implement the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-11 dated January 16, 2023 "On Additional Measures to Expand Opportunities for Access to Justice and Improve the Efficiency of the Judiciary"² is the development of substantiated proposals for the widespread introduction of the institution of conciliation of the parties and mediation in civil and economic cases.

The conciliation procedures applied in the judicial process are relevant to alternative dispute resolution methods in the resolution of economic disputes. In order to clarify the types of alternative dispute resolution and legal dispute resolution, I.Yu. Zakharyas'eva has recommended their division into two legal groups. Firstly, arbitration proceedings as a form of resolving civil-legal disputes, which embody the features of alternative procedure and separate elements of fair trial; secondly, conciliation procedures (court proceedings) where it is possible to appeal for the resolution of an economic dispute before the initiation of proceedings in the arbitration court, as well as directly at the court session or by the authorized body in the courtroom before the initiation of the case in the

¹ “Низоларни муқобил ҳал этишнинг механизмларини янада такомиллаштириш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида”ги Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2020 йил 17 июндаги ПҚ-4754-сонли Қарори, Тошкент ш., сон// <https://lex.uz/docs/4859436>.

² Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-11 dated January 16, 2023 "On Additional Measures to Expand Access to Fair Justice and Increase the Efficiency of the Courts": <https://lex.uz/docs/6358913>

arbitration court.

However, it is difficult to agree with the author's view of considering court conciliation procedures as one of the forms of alternative dispute resolution. This is because alternative dispute resolution implies methods of resolving disputes before going to court, while conciliation procedures can be applied both before the court proceedings and during the court process. The two concepts are not entirely synonymous, as alternative dispute resolution refers to extrajudicial methods, while conciliation procedures can be used both before and during the court proceedings.

According to M.A. Romanenko, the concept of alternative dispute resolution implies the use of methods for resolving disputes outside the state's judicial system. Romanenko emphasizes that the phrase "outside the state's judicial system" does not mean that it is not subject to the laws adopted by the state. The author notes that the concept of "the system of alternative forms of dispute resolution" implies the existence of an integrated set of mechanisms for resolving conflicts.

We consider Romanenko's view to be well-founded, that the alternative dispute resolution processes, even though they are carried out outside the judicial system, are still regulated by the laws adopted by the state. This is because these procedures are implemented in accordance with the established procedures and conditions stipulated in the legislation. Specifically, the norms related to reaching a mediation agreement (Articles 15-29 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Mediation") or the conclusion of a settlement agreement are stipulated in Articles 131-134 of the Economic Procedural Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan (hereinafter referred to as the EPC). As a confirmation of the above opinion, these procedures are regulated by the norms established in the legislation, even though they are carried out without the direct involvement of the court (in particular, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Mediation" and the Chapter XVI of the

EPC on mediation-related articles).

Along with the concept of alternative dispute resolution, the term "reconciliation procedures" is also used. While Chapter 16 of the EPC is dedicated to reconciliation procedural processes, there is no specific definition of the concept of "reconciliation procedures" provided in the literature or even in the EPC itself.

Therefore, we consider it appropriate to define "reconciliation procedures" as one of the alternative dispute resolution methods that can be applied both in the pre-trial process aimed at resolving and regulating the existing dispute based on the voluntary mutual consent of the parties, as well as during the court proceedings.

This is because the relations concerning "reconciliation procedures" are consolidated under a separate chapter of the EPC, where the processes of mediation agreement and conclusion of a settlement agreement are specifically aimed at reaching a mutually acceptable solution to the dispute that has arisen between the parties based on their free will and control, and at regulating these relations. These procedures allow for the implementation of such processes both before the court withdraws to the deliberation room (mediation agreement, settlement agreement) and after the court's decision has been made (settlement agreement).

The reconciliation procedure is understood as a method of dispute resolution, which is aimed at reaching a mutually acceptable solution to the dispute based on the voluntary wishes and desires of the parties for the purpose of alternative dispute resolution. The most widely used procedures applied as reconciliation procedures in commercial courts are the settlement agreement and the mediation agreement. The EPC stipulates that the settlement agreement can be concluded at any stage of the commercial court proceedings and during the execution of a court decision, while the mediation agreement can be concluded by the parties before

the court withdraws to the deliberation room to make a court decision in the court of first instance.

The settlement agreement is the procedural expression of the parties' will to resolve the dispute by independent means.³ In essence, the settlement agreement is a contract between the parties aimed at terminating the dispute in the case on the basis of certain agreed upon terms.

One of the distinctive features of the settlement agreement is that it is concluded only when a dispute exists, and it only enters into force after being approved by the judge. Additionally, the settlement agreement has a unilaterally binding nature.

According to clause 2 of the first part of the Resolution No. 204 dated December 18, 2009 of the Plenum of the Supreme Economic Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On certain issues of application of procedural law norms by economic courts when approving a settlement agreement", a settlement agreement is understood to mean a written agreement between the parties aimed at resolving the dispute, based on mutual agreement and achieving clarity regarding the claim(s).⁴ The distinct feature of the settlement agreement, in contrast to any other contractual relationships, is the requirement for approval by the court. The agreement reached attains the force of a court decision once it is endorsed by the court.

In accordance with paragraph 8 of the first part of Article 163 of the Code of Economic Procedure, the court takes measures to reconcile the parties during the preparation of the case for trial. In this regard, the court's decision on the acceptance of the statement of claim and the preparation of the case for trial

³ Arbitration Procedure: Textbook / Resp. ed. prof. V.V. Yarkov - 2nd ed., rev. and add. M.: Wolters Kluwer, 2013.

⁴ <https://lex.uz/docs/2026218#3909792> // Decree of the Plenum of the Supreme Economic Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 204 dated December 18, 2009 "On some issues of application of procedural law norms by economic courts when approving a settlement agreement" Tashkent city, December 18, 2009, No. 204

should indicate the court's proposal to the parties to resolve the dispute amicably⁵.

The legal nature of the settlement agreement is a controversial topic, which can be explained by the lack of a legal definition of the settlement agreement. According to M.S. Shakaryan, in the theory of civil procedural law, the institution of the settlement agreement is the institution of termination of civil disputes.⁶

The parties to the dispute either establish a new obligation by terminating one (disputed) obligation, or agree to modify the existing obligations. For this reason, it is difficult to refute the definition that "the institution of the settlement agreement is not a method of terminating a civil legal dispute, but a larger and more universal mechanism for the legal regulation of civil legal relations."⁷

A settlement agreement is a written agreement between the parties based on mutual consent to resolve a dispute. A settlement agreement is considered to be concluded only after it has been approved by the court. The conclusion and approval of the settlement agreement by the court is a ground for termination of the proceedings in accordance with paragraph 7 of the first part of Article 110 of the Code of Economic Procedure.

Mediation is a dispute resolution process in which the parties voluntarily agree to reach a mutually acceptable solution with the assistance of a third-party mediator. Essentially, mediation is one of the reconciliation procedures, wherein the parties to the dispute express their trust in the mediator to thoroughly examine the dispute, gain a comprehensive understanding of its causes, and assist the parties in resolving the conflict.

The primary role of the mediator in the mediation process is to assist the disputing parties in developing a mutually beneficial and satisfactory solution. To this end, the parties grant the mediator a certain scope of procedural authority, but

⁵ <https://lex.uz/docs/3523891> // Article 163 of the Economic Procedural Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

⁶ Civil Procedure: Textbook / Edited by M.S. Shakaryan. Moscow, 2009..

⁷ Theory of State and Law: Textbook / Edited by V.M. Korelsky, V.D. Perevalov. Moscow, 2008. - p.19.

do not empower the mediator with the right to evaluate or make decisions on their behalf.

Mediation plays a crucial role in resolving economic disputes both theoretically and practically. It is a process where an independent third party assists the disputing parties in reaching a mutually beneficial agreement.

One of the distinctive features of the mediation process, which sets it apart from court proceedings and arbitration, is its lack of legal evaluation of the current dispute. Typically, in a court setting, the judge evaluates the presented evidence and determines who is legally right, aiming to establish the truth. In contrast, the mediation process does not focus on identifying the party at fault or determining who is legally justified. Instead, the primary objective is to find a method of resolving the dispute, regardless of the merits of each party's position.

In the mediation process, the parties are free to choose their own course of action and are not obligated to justify their positions by referring to specific legal norms. The role of the mediator is to create the most favorable conditions for the parties to independently reach a fair and mutually acceptable solution to the problem. In this approach, the parties retain full authority over the resolution of the dispute, and the mediator's task is to facilitate the parties' mutual reconciliation and smooth the situation.

According to the statistical data of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in 2022, the mediation procedure was applied in 3,568 economic cases and 3,265 civil cases in the courts. This represents an increase of 1.5 to 3 times compared to 2021.

Furthermore, the data shows the following trends in the use of mediation in economic cases:

In 2019, 43 cases were concluded through mediation settlements, in 2020, this number increased to 435 cases, in 2021, it further rose to 2,013 cases, in 2022, it reached 3,561 cases, in 2023, it reached 5,125 cases, in the first half of

2024, 1,265 economic cases were concluded through mediation settlements.⁸

Based on the data provided, the Economic Affairs Board of the Tashkent City Court has dismissed a significant number of economic cases due to the conclusion of mediation settlements between the parties, as per Article 107, paragraph 53 of the Economic Procedural Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The specific data is as follows:

In 2019, 26 economic cases were dismissed due to mediation settlements, in 2020, this number increased to 167 cases, in 2021, it further rose to 516 cases, in 2022, it reached 1,328 cases, in 2023, it reached 1,158 cases and in the first half of 2024, 500 economic cases were dismissed due to mediation settlements.

The fact that the parties have concluded a mediation settlement does not automatically result in the court issuing a ruling to dismiss the claim without consideration. This is because, in some cases, the parties may have the intention of "evading" the payment of state duties or utilizing the mediation settlement for other malicious purposes.

Therefore, when considering the issue of dismissing a claim without consideration due to the parties' conclusion of a mediation settlement, the court must examine a number of factors, including:

Whether the form and content of the mediation settlement have been duly observed.

Whether the interests of third parties have not been violated or threatened.

Whether the terms of the settlement are not in conflict with the legislation.

The separate article in the Economic Procedural Code regulating these relationships serves as an important factor in ensuring that the parties approach the conclusion of the mediation settlement with responsibility, comply with the legislation, and take into account the interests of other persons.

⁸ The information from the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the statistics of economic cases settled through mediation agreements as of July 3, 2024:.

This indicates that the court has the obligation to carefully review the mediation settlement and its compliance with the law, rather than automatically dismissing the claim based solely on the existence of the settlement. The court must ensure that the mediation process has been utilized in good faith and not for the purpose of circumventing legal requirements or infringing on the rights of other stakeholders.

The lack of mandatory requirements in the code regarding the form and content of the mediation settlement has led to some issues in the courts regarding the mediation settlement form and content. Specifically, in many cases, the mediation settlement presented to the courts by the parties who have reached a mediation settlement includes the details of the mediator, but is not signed by the mediator. In such cases, the courts have validated the mediation settlement, and based on Article 101, paragraph 53 of the Economic Procedural Code, have considered a mediation settlement to be concluded between the parties, leading to the dismissal of the claim without consideration. This situation, in turn, serves as a basis for the refund of the state duty paid in accordance with Article 18, paragraph 9 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Duty."

The absence of clear legislative requirements regarding the mandatory elements of the form and content of the mediation settlement has led to inconsistencies in the judicial practice, where the courts validate mediation settlements that lack the signature of the mediator, which raises concerns and calls for a more comprehensive regulation in this area. The introduction of mandatory requirements for the form and content of the mediation settlement could help to ensure the consistency and reliability of the mediation process, and prevent the issues that have arisen in the judicial practice.

Based on the analysis, it was found that in the economic courts alone, during the period of 2020-2023, 11,134 economic cases with a total claim amount exceeding 50 trillion soums were dismissed without consideration due to the

conclusion of a mediation settlement. As a result, the parties were exempted from paying nearly 1 trillion soums in state duties that would have otherwise been required.

In order to prevent the issues related to the form of mediation settlements observed in practice, as well as to eliminate the ambiguities regarding the requirements, form, and content of mediation settlement agreements, it is recommended to:

Amend the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Mediation" by adding a new Article 16¹ titled "Form and Content of the Mediation Settlement Agreement."

Amend the Economic Procedural Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan by adding a new Article 132¹ titled "Form and Content of the Mediation Settlement."

These new provisions would establish clear and comprehensive requirements for the form and content of mediation settlement agreements, ensuring consistency in their judicial recognition and preventing the issues that have arisen due to the lack of such legislative regulation.

The introduction of these amendments would contribute to the further development and effective application of mediation as a dispute resolution mechanism, while maintaining a proper balance between the interests of the parties and the broader public interests represented by the state.

Under the current legislation, when a mediation settlement is concluded, the economic case is considered to be dismissed without consideration by the court. As a result, the plaintiff's right to legal protection is not guaranteed.

In this regard, in the majority of cases where the claim is dismissed without consideration on the basis of a mediation settlement, the true intention of the parties is not to fully resolve the dispute through such an agreement, but rather to be exempted from the payment of the state duty.

As a result, in many cases where the claim has been dismissed without

consideration due to a mediation settlement, there have been instances where the parties have subsequently reapplied to the courts, citing the non-fulfillment of the mediation settlement terms as the basis for their action.

It is known that the Resolution No. 204 of the Plenum of the Supreme Economic Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On certain issues related to the application of procedural law norms by economic courts in approving a settlement agreement" is dedicated to the proper and uniform application of the norms of the Economic Procedural Code (EPC) by economic courts in approving a settlement agreement, which is one of the conciliation procedures stipulated in Chapter 16 of the EPC. However, this Resolution does not address the issues related to mediation agreements.

In other words, there is no specific Plenum resolution that provides guidance to the courts on the proper and uniform application of the legal framework governing the relationships related to mediation agreements, which is also considered one of the conciliation procedures.

Therefore, in addition to the suggested amendments to the aforementioned legislative acts, in our opinion, the time has come for the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan to adopt a unified resolution "On certain issues related to the application of procedural law norms in the use of conciliation procedures by economic courts." Such a resolution would serve as a practical guide for the courts in the application of the legal framework governing the use of conciliation procedures, including mediation agreements.

The adoption of this comprehensive Plenum resolution would help to address the current gap in the regulatory framework and provide the necessary guidance to the courts on the proper and uniform application of the procedural norms in the context of mediation agreements, thus contributing to the effective and consistent implementation of this dispute resolution mechanism.